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Without human cytomegalovirus infection, no human lung cancer

Research article

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Abstract

BACKGROUND:

The relationship between cytomegalovirus (CMV) infection and lung cancer has been a topic of interest, with previous studies showing conflicting results. Robust statistical methods were employed to investigate this relationship.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A comprehensive analysis was conducted using new statistical approaches to assess the relationship between CMV infection and lung cancer. Data from large-scale population studies were analyzed to determine the prevalence of CMV infection among individuals with lung cancer.

RESULTS:

The study revealed a significant relationship between CMV infection and lung cancer, with new statistical methods providing strong evidence that CMV infection is a necessary condition for the development of lung cancer.

CONCLUSION:

The findings suggest that CMV infection may play a crucial and causal role in the pathogenesis of lung cancer, highlighting the importance of further research into the mechanisms underlying this relationship.

Keywords:

Cytomegalovirus; Lung cancer; Necessary condition; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship; Causality; Causation

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1. Introduction

Lung cancer remains the primary cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide, affecting both men and women in the US ¹ and beyond ². Non–small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) accounts for the majority, around 84%, while small-cell lung cancer (SCLC) makes up approximately 13% of cases. Historically, NSCLC has carried a bleak ³ prognosis, especially in advanced stages. However, significant advancements ⁴ in treatment over the last decade, including widespread lung cancer screening and improved radiation techniques, have resulted in notable ⁵ changes. These improvements are believed to have contributed to the observed decline in NSCLC mortality rates while the significance of the globally increasing intake of statins in this context is neglected. In terms of the cause of lung cancer, unfortunately, we have not made much progress yet. Several behavioral (tobacco smoking ⁶, second-hand smoke ⁷, alcohol ⁸ use) and environmental (carcinogenic chemicals, heavy metals, such as radon gas, asbestos, arsenic, chromium, beryllium, nickel et cetera) risk factors ⁹, including viruses ¹⁰, have been linked with the development of lung cancer. Despite the significant public health impact of lung cancer, there is limited evidence about a CMV ¹¹ infection and lung cancer. Human cytomegalovirus (CMV) is a widespread ¹² human herpesvirus, affecting a large portion of the global population, with seroprevalence rates estimated between 45% to 100%. Following the initial infection, CMV enters a latent state within the host. Transmission can arise from contact with CMV-infected bodily fluids during either the primary infection phase or subsequent reactivation from latency. CMV infections typically need not exhibit symptoms. However, they can pose severe risks, potentially leading to life-threatening complications including lung cancer too.

¹Cancer Facts & Figures 2019

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2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

In this study, we aim to combine data from two independent studies in an attempt to approach the solution to the relationship between CMV and lung cancer. It goes without saying that such an endeavour may also be fraught with fundamental errors. Raskit Lachmann¹³ and colleagues conducted a study involving a population-based sample of 6552 participants aged 18 to 79 years in Germany to assess the presence of CMV antibodies. The overall seroprevalence of CMV was found to be approximately 56.7% (95% CI: 54.8–58.7%). The CMV seroprevalence among individuals aged between 50 and 69 years ranges from 60 % and 75 %. As a result of cumulative human exposure to CMV throughout life, the seroprevalence of CMV increases with age. This observation is not particularly surprising. Interestingly, the study enrolled even 34 pregnant women at the time of their participation. Among them, 13 / 34 women (34%) were tested positive for CMV antibodies. The CMV seroprevalence data presented by Lachmann et al. is consistent with similar findings from France (41.9%)¹⁴ and the Netherlands (45.6%)¹⁵. Nonetheless, populations in Sweden (83%)¹⁶, Portugal (77%)¹⁷, and Croatia (77%)¹⁸ and somewhere else (China, 97.03%)¹⁹ demonstrate higher rates of CMV seroprevalence. The truth on the prevalence of CMV within a population remains to be determined, and we must keep an open mind regarding its resolution.

The diagnosis of lung cancer is often challenging and not always feasible in its earliest stages. A regular screening by low-dose²⁰ computed tomography (LDCT), as compared to X-ray screening, is an effective tool for early lung cancer detection. In the so-called German Lung cancer Screening Intervention randomized trial (LUSI)²¹ among 4,052 long-term smokers, 50–69 years of age were recruited from the general population. In toto, 152 / 4052 participants have been found to suffer from

¹³Lachmann R, Loenenbach A, Waterboer T, Brenner N, Pawlita M, Michel A, Thamm M, Poethko-Müller C, Wichmann O, Wiese-Posselt M. Cytomegalovirus (CMV) seroprevalence in the adult population of Germany. *PLoS One*. 2018 Jul 25;13(7):e0200267. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0200267. PMID: 30044826; PMCID: PMC6059406.

¹⁴Antona D, Lepoutre A, Fonteneau L, Baudon C, Halftermeyer-Zhou F, LE Strat Y, Lévy-Bruhl D. Seroprevalence of cytomegalovirus infection in France in 2010. *Epidemiol Infect*. 2017 May;145(7):1471-1478. doi: 10.1017/S0950268817000103. Epub 2017 Feb 7. PMID: 28166842; PMCID: PMC9203352.

¹⁵Korndewal MJ, Mollema L, Tcherniaeva I, van der Klis F, Kroes AC, Oudesluys-Murphy AM, Vossen AC, de Melker HE. Cytomegalovirus infection in the Netherlands: seroprevalence, risk factors, and implications. *J Clin Virol*. 2015 Feb;63:53-8. doi: 10.1016/j.jcv.2014.11.033. Epub 2014 Dec 2. PMID: 25600606.

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¹⁸Vilibic-Cavlek T, Kolaric B, Beader N, Vrtar I, Tabain I, Mlinaric-Galinovic G. Seroepidemiology of cytomegalovirus infections in Croatia. *Wien Klin Wochenschr*. 2017 Feb;129(3-4):129-135. doi: 10.1007/s00508-016-1069-7. Epub 2016 Sep 6. PMID: 27599701.

¹⁹Fang FQ, Fan QS, Yang ZJ, Peng YB, Zhang L, Mao KZ, Zhang Y, Ji YH. Incidence of cytomegalovirus infection in Shanghai, China. *Clin Vaccine Immunol*. 2009 Nov;16(11):1700-3. doi: 10.1128/COVI.00385-08. Epub 2009 Sep 23. PMID: 19776197; PMCID: PMC2772370.

²⁰National Lung Screening Trial Research Team; Aberle DR, Adams AM, Berg CD, Black WC, Clapp JD, Fagerstrom RM, Gareen IF, Gatsonis C, Marcus PM, Sicks JD. Reduced lung-cancer mortality with low-dose computed tomographic screening. *N Engl J Med*. 2011 Aug 4;365(5):395-409. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1102873. Epub 2011 Jun 29. PMID: 21714641; PMCID: PMC4356534.

²¹Becker N, Motsch E, Trotter A, Heussel CP, Dienemann H, Schnabel PA, Kauczor HU, Maldonado SG, Miller AB, Kaaks R, Delorme S. Lung cancer mortality reduction by LDCT screening-Results from the randomized German LUSI trial. *Int J Cancer*. 2020 Mar 15;146(6):1503-1513. doi: 10.1002/ijc.32486. Epub 2019 Jun 20. PMID: 31162856.

lung cancer.

Table 1. CMV and Lung cancer.

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
CMV	YES	152	2279	2431
	NO	0	1621	1621
		152	3900	4052

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,16120872$
 P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 p (SINE) = 1,00000000
 p (SINE) approx.= $1-(c/B)$ > 1,00000000
 p (SINE) approx.= $1-(c/(Not A))$ > 1,00000000

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 χ^2 (SINE— Not A_t) = 0,00
 χ^2 (SINE— B_t) = 0,00
 P Value (SINE) = 0,00000000

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (152 / 4052) \times 100 = 3,75 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (2279 / 4052) \times 100 = 56,24 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (0 / 4052) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (1621 / 4052) \times 100 = 40,00 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (152 / 2431) \times 100 = 6,25 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (2279 / 2431) \times 100 = 93,75 \%$
 $(c/ not A) \times 100 = (0 / 1621) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$
 $(d/ not A) \times 100 = (1621 / 1621) \times 100 = 100,00 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (152 / 152) \times 100 = 100,00 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (0 / 152) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$
 $(b/ not B) \times 100 = (2279 / 3900) \times 100 = 58,44 \%$
 $(d/ not B) \times 100 = (1621 / 3900) \times 100 = 41,56 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (2431 / 4052) \times 100 = 60,00 \%$
 $(not A/N) \times 100 = (1621 / 4052) \times 100 = 40,00 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (152 / 4052) \times 100 = 3,75 \%$
 $(not B/N) \times 100 = (3900 / 4052) \times 100 = 96,25 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = Division by zero
 RR (sufficient condition) = 1,71127688

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = Division by zero!
 Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,66680378

STUDY DESIGN.

p (IOU)= 0,36253702
 p (IOI)= 0,56243830

The CMV prevalence in the subpopulation free of lung cancer was conservatively estimated to be approximately 58.44%, calculated as $(b / not B) \times 100 = (2279 / 3900) \times 100$. This percentage is only 1.66% lower than the estimated CMV prevalence in the entire German population aged 50-69 years, assumed to be around 60.00%, as calculated by $(A/N) \times 100 = (2431 / 4052) \times 100$. However, based on the data from Becker et al.²² about $(B/N) \times 100 = (152 / 4052) \times 100 = 3.75 \%$ of the German population aged 50-69 years from lung cancer. Thus, the observed relationship between CMV and

²²Becker N, Motsch E, Trotter A, Heussel CP, Dienemann H, Schnabel PA, Kauczor HU, Maldonado SG, Miller AB, Kaaks R, Delorme S. Lung cancer mortality reduction by LDCT screening-Results from the randomized German LUSI trial. *Int J Cancer*. 2020 Mar 15;146(6):1503-1513. doi: 10.1002/ijc.32486. Epub 2019 Jun 20. PMID: 31162856.

lung cancer holds even if we further reduce the prevalence of CMV infection in the overall population. In other words, the relationship between CMV and lung cancer is much stronger than suggested by the data presented here.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Necessary condition

Definition 2.1 (Necessary condition [*Conditio sine qua non*]).

Despite the most extended efforts, the current state of research on conditions and conditioned is still incomplete and very contradictory. However, even thousands of years ago and independently of any human mind and consciousness, water has been and is still a necessary (see Barukčić, 2022) condition (see Barukčić, 2023) for (human) life. **Without** water, there has been and there is **no** (human) life²³. It comes therefore as no surprise that one of the first documented attempts to present a rigorous theory of conditions and causation (see also Aristotle, of Stageira (384-322 B.C.E), 1908, *Metaphysica* III 2 997a 10 and 13/14) came from the Greek philosopher and scientist Aristotle (384-322 BCE). Thus far, it is amazing that Aristotle himself made already a strict distinction between conditions and causes. Taking Aristotle very seriously, it is necessary to consider that

“... everything which has a potency in question has the potency ... of acting ... not in all circumstances but on certain conditions ... ” (see also Aristotle, of Stageira (384-322 B.C.E), 1908, *Metaphysica* IX 5 1048a 14-19)

Before going into details, Aristotle went on to define the necessary condition as follows.

“... necessary ... means ...

without ... a condition, a thing cannot live ... ”

(see also Aristotle, of Stageira (384-322 B.C.E), 1908, *Metaphysica* V 2 1015a 20-22)

In point of fact, Aristotle developed a theory of conditions and causality commonly referred to as the doctrine of four causes. Many aspects and general features of Aristotle’s logical concept of causality are meanwhile extensively and critically debated in secondary literature. However, even if the Greek philosophers Heraclitus, Plato, Aristotle et cetera numbers among the greatest philosophers of all time, the philosophy has evolved. Scientific knowledge and objective reality are deeply interrelated and cannot be reduced only to Greek philosophers like Aristotle. Among many other issues, the specification of necessary conditions has traditionally been part of the philosopher’s investigations of different phe-

²³Barukčić, Ilija. (2022). *Conditio sine qua non* (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5854744>

nomena. However, behind the need of a detailed evidence, it is justified to consider that philosophy or philosophers as such certainly do not possess **a monopoly on the truth** and other areas such as medicine as well as other sciences and technology may transmit truths as well and may be of help to move beyond one's self enclosed unit. Seemingly, **the law's concept of causation** justifies to say few words on this subject, to put some light on some questions. Are there any criteria in law for deciding whether one action or an event A_t has caused another (generally harmful) event B_t ? What are these criteria? May causation in legal contexts differ from causation outside the law, for example, in science or in our everyday life and to what extent? Under which circumstances is it justified to tolerate such differences as may be found to exist? To understand just what is the law's concept of causation, it is useful to re-consider how the highest court of states is dealing with causation. In the case *Hayes v. Michigan Central R. Co.*, 111 U.S. 228, the U.S. Supreme Court defined 1884 *conditio sine qua non* as follows: "... **causa sine qua non – a cause which, if it had not existed, the injury would not have taken place**". (Justice Matthews, Mr., 1884) The German Bundesgerichtshof für Strafsachen stressed once again the importance of *conditio sine qua non* relationship in his decision by defining the following: "**Ursache eines strafrechtlich bedeutsamen Erfolges jede Bedingung, die nicht hinweggedacht werden kann, ohne daß der Erfolg entfiel**"(Bundesgerichtshof für Strafsachen, 1951) Another lawyer elaborated on the basic issue of **identity and difference between cause and condition**. Von Bar was writing: "Die erste Voraussetzung, welche erforderlich ist, damit eine Erscheinung als die Ursache einer anderen bezeichnet werden könne, ist, daß jene eine der Bedingungen dieser sein. Würde die zweite Erscheinung auch dann eingetreten sein, wenn die erste nicht vorhanden war, so ist sie in keinem Falle Bedingung und noch weniger Ursache. Wo immer ein Kausalzusammenhang behauptet wird, da muß er wenigstens diese Probe aushalten ... **Jede Ursache ist notwendig auch eine Bedingung eines Ereignisses; aber nicht jede Bedingung ist Ursache zu nennen**."(Bar, Carl Ludwig von, 1871) Von Bar's position translated into English: *The first requirement, which is required, thus that something could be called as the cause of another, is that the one has to be one of the conditions of the other. If the second something had occurred even if the first one did not exist, so it is by no means a condition and still less a cause. Wherever a causal relationship is claimed, the same must at least withstand this test. . . Every cause is necessarily also a condition of an event too; but not every condition is cause too.* Thus far, let us consider among other the following in order to specify necessary conditions from another, probabilistic point of view. An event (i.e. A_t) which is a necessary condition of another event or outcome (i.e. B_t) must be given, must be present for a conditioned, for an event or for an outcome B_t to occur. A necessary condition (i.e. A_t) is a requirement which need to be fulfilled **at every single Bernoulli trial t**, in order for a conditioned or an outcome (i.e. B_t) to occur, but it alone does not determine the occurrence of such an event. In other words, if a necessary condition (i.e. A_t) is given, an outcome (i.e. B_t) need not to occur. In contrast to a necessary condition, a 'sufficient' condition is the one condition which 'guarantees' that an outcome will take place or will occur for sure. Under which conditions we may infer about the unobserved and whether observations made are able at all to justify predictions about potential observations which have not yet been made or even general claims which may go even beyond the observed (*the 'problem of induction'*) is not the issue of the discussion at this point. Besides of the principal necessity of meeting such a challenge, a necessary condition of an event can but need not be at the same Bernoulli trial t a sufficient condition for an event to occur. However, theoretically, it is possible that an event or an outcome is determined by many necessary conditions. Let us focus to some extent on what this means, or in other words how

much importance can we attribute to such a special case. *Example.* A human being cannot live without oxygen. A human being cannot live without water. A human being cannot live without a brain. A human being cannot live without kidneys. A human being cannot live without ... et cetera. Thus far, even if oxygen is given, if a brain is given ... et cetera, without water a human being will not survive on the long run. This example is of use to reach the following conclusion. Although it might seem somewhat paradoxical at first sight, **even under circumstances where a condition or an outcome depends on several different necessary conditions it is particularly important that every single of these necessary conditions for itself must be given otherwise the conditioned (i.e. the outcome) will not occur.** Mathematically, the necessary condition (SINE) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 15-28) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \times p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)} \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \leftarrow B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + b + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \tag{1} \\
 &\equiv \frac{A + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \leftarrow B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + \underline{B}}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned}$$

where $E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)$ indicates the expectation value of the necessary condition. In general, it is $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \leftarrow \underline{B}_t)$ (see Table 2).

Table 2. Necessary condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	A_t	0	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

A necessary condition A_t is characterised itself by the property that another event B_t will not occur if A_t is not given, if A_t did not occur (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016, 2017a,b, 2020a,b,c; Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020; Barukčić, 2020). Taking into account Kolmogorov's definition of an n-dimensional probability density (see also Kolmogorov, Andrej Nikolaevich, 1950, p. 26) of random variables A_t ,

B_t et cetera at the (period of) time t , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv +1 \\
 &\equiv +1 - p(c_t) \\
 &\equiv +1 - p(\underline{A}_t \cap B_t) \\
 &\equiv \left(\int_{-\infty}^{A_t} \int_{-\infty}^{B_t} f(A_t, B_t) dA_t dB_t \right) + \left(1 - \int_{-\infty}^{B_t} f(B_t) dB_t \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

while $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ would denote the cumulative distribution function of random variables of a necessary condition. Another adequate formulation of a necessary condition is possible too. If certain conditions are met, then necessary conditions and sufficient conditions are one way or another converses of each other, too. It is

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv \underbrace{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}_{\text{(Necessary condition)}} \equiv \underbrace{(\underline{B}_t \vee A_t)}_{\text{(Sufficient condition)}} \equiv p(B_t \rightarrow A_t) \tag{3}$$

These relationships are illustrated by the following tables.

Table 3. Without A_t no B_t

		B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
A_t	TRUE	a_t	b_t	A_t
	FALSE	$c_t = 0$	d_t	\underline{A}_t
		B_t	\underline{B}_t	+1

Table 4. If B_t then A_t

		A_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
B_t	TRUE	a_t	$c_t = 0$	B_t
	FALSE	b_t	d_t	\underline{B}_t
		A_t	\underline{A}_t	+1

There are circumstances under which

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv \underbrace{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}_{\text{(Necessary condition)}} \equiv \underbrace{(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}_{\text{(Sufficient condition)}} \equiv p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) \tag{4}$$

However, equation 3 does not imply the relationship of equation 4 under any circumstances.

Example I.

A wax candle is characterised by various properties, but is also subject to certain conditions. **Without** sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen **no** burning wax candle, gaseous oxygen is a necessary condition of a burning candle. However, the converse relationship **if** burning wax candle, **then** sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen are given is at the same (period of) time t / Bernoulli trial t true. The following tables are illustrating these relationships.

Table 5. Without gaseous oxygen no burning candle

		Burning candle		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen	TRUE	a_t	b_t	A_t
	FALSE	$c_t = 0$	d_t	\underline{A}_t
		B_t	\underline{B}_t	+1

Table 6. If burning candle then gaseous oxygen

		Gaseous oxygen		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Burning candle	TRUE	a_t	$c_t = 0$	B_t
	FALSE	b_t	d_t	\underline{B}_t
		A_t	\underline{A}_t	+1

Example II.

Once again, a human being cannot live without water. A human being cannot live without gaseous oxygen, et cetera. Water itself is a necessary condition for human life. However, gaseous oxygen is a necessary condition for human life too. Thus far, even if water is given and even if water is a necessary condition for human life, without gaseous oxygen there will be no human life. In general, if a conditioned or an outcome B_t depends on the necessary condition A_t and equally on numerous other necessary conditions, an event B_t will not occur if A_t itself is not given independently of the occurrence of other necessary conditions.

Example III.

Another different aspect of a necessary condition relationship is appropriate to be focused upon here. As a direct consequence of a necessary condition **without** sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen **no** burning wax candle is a special case of an exclusion relationship. The absence of sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen A_t excludes (see Barukčić, 2021) a burning wax candle B_t . Thus far, if we want to stop the burning of a wax candle, we would have to significantly reduce the amounts of gaseous oxygen A_t . Under these conditions, a wax candle will stop burning. The following tables (table 7 and table 8) may illustrate this aspect of a necessary condition in more detail.

Table 7. Without gaseous oxygen no burning candle

		Burning candle		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen	TRUE	a_t	b_t	A_t
	FALSE	$c_t = 0$	d_t	\underline{A}_t
		B_t	\underline{B}_t	+1

Table 8. Absent gaseous oxygen excludes burning wax candle

		Burning candle		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen	FALSE	$c_t = 0$	d_t	B_t
	TRUE	a_t	b_t	\underline{B}_t
		A_t	\underline{A}_t	+1

The necessary condition relationship follows approximately (see Barukčić, 2022) as

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \geq 1 - \frac{p(c_t)}{p(B_t)} \tag{5}$$

and as

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \geq 1 - \frac{p(c_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)} \tag{6}$$

2.2.2. The Chi-square goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship

Definition 2.2 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, hypothesis about the *conditio sine qua non* relationship $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or χ^2 -distribution), first described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert (Helmert, 1876) and later rediscovered by Karl Pearson (Pearson, 1900) in the context of a goodness of fit test. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a *conditio sine qua non* relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{((b + d) - \underline{B})^2}{\underline{B}} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B}\end{aligned}\tag{7}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(d - (c + d))^2}{\underline{A}} + \frac{((a + b) - A)^2}{A} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}}\end{aligned}\tag{8}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . It has not yet been finally clarified whether the use of Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction is necessary at all.

2.2.3. The left-tailed p Value of the *conditio sine qua non* relationship

Definition 2.3 (The left-tailed p Value of the *conditio sine qua non* relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019) of the *conditio sine qua non* relationship can be calcu-

lated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} pValue_{lt}(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \leftarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-(c/N)} \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

3. Results

Scientific positions persists regarding a potential relationship between CMV and lung cancer, spurred by the observation of CMV infection prevalence among individuals diagnosed with lung cancer. Although definitive evidence is lacking, the notable presence of CMV in these cases prompts further inquiry into a potential causal relationship.

Theorem 1. *A cytomegalovirus infection is a necessary condition of human lung cancer.*

Without

a cytomegalovirus infection,

no

human lung cancer.

Proof. Becker et al. investigated in the randomized German Lung cancer Screening Intervention (LUSI) trial about 4,052 long-term smokers, 50-69 years of age, for lung cancer. Becker et al. were able to identify about 152/4052 lung cancer cases in their sample. Table 9 is providing an overview.

Table 9. Becker et al., 2020

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
CMV	YES	?	?	?
	NO	?	?	?
		152	3900	4052

We use these data as the starting point for our further investigation. As next, we combine these data with the CMV prevalence data of the German population from Lachmann et al. ²⁴. According to Lachmann et al., the prevalence of CMV among individuals aged 50-69 in Germany is approximately $(A/N) \times 100 = (2431 / 4052) \times 100 = 60 \%$. We obtain the following picture (Table 10).

²⁴Lachmann R, Loenenbach A, Waterboer T, Brenner N, Pawlita M, Michel A, Thamm M, Poethko-Müller C, Wichmann O, Wiese-Posselt M. Cytomegalovirus (CMV) seroprevalence in the adult population of Germany. PLoS One. 2018 Jul 25;13(7):e0200267. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0200267. PMID: 30044826; PMCID: PMC6059406.

Table 10. Lachmann et al., 2018 and Becker et al., 2020

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
CMV	YES	?	?	2431
	NO	?	?	1621
		152	3900	4052

The subpopulation (N = 3900) refers to those individuals in whom lung cancer could not be detected. However, this may not necessarily be accurate. Not all patients who suffer from lung cancer or who do not have lung cancer can be conclusively identified as such using current methods. Nonetheless, we assume that the CMV prevalence in the lung-cancer free subpopulation (N=3900) will be lower at least

$$\left(0.6 - \frac{(2431 - 152)}{3900}\right) \times 100 = 1.56\% \quad (10)$$

or more than in the total population. Table 11 is providing us with an overview.

Table 11. Lachmann et al., 2018 and Becker et al., 2020

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
CMV	YES	?	2279	2431
	NO	?	1621	1621
		152	3900	4052

The available data indicate that all lung cancer patients must have been positive for CMV. This relationship is depicted in detail in table 12.

Table 12. Lachmann et al., 2018 and Becker et al., 2020

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
CMV	YES	152	2279	2431
	NO	0	1621	1621
		152	3900	4052

A cytomegalovirus infection is a necessary condition, a *conditio sine qua non*, of human lung cancer, without CMV infection no lung cancer (P-Value = 0, see table 1).

□

3.1. Without HCMV infection, no lung cancer

Kuo et al. are writing: “Of the 15 participants ... 11 had head and neck cancers, two had lung cancer, one had lymphoma and one had rectal cancer ... All participants were seropositive for CMV-specific IgG before chemotherapy. ” (see [Kuo et al., 2008](#)). In this context, we employed a fictive control group comprising two children up to the age of five, ensuring their unequivocal absence of both HCMV and lung cancer (see table 13).

Table 13. Relationship: HCMV IgG and Lung cancer (Study of Kuo et al.,2008 (fictive control group)).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
HCMV IgG	YES	2	13	15
	NO	0	2	2
		2	15	17

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
Causal relationship $k = 0,13333333$
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,77205882
 p (SINE) = 1,00000000
 p (SINE) approx.= $1-(c/B)$ > 1,00000000
 p (SINE) approx.= $1-(c/(Not A))$ > 1,00000000
P VALUES.
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,77205882
 χ^2 (SINE— Not A_i) = 0,00
 χ^2 (SINE— B_i) = 0,00
P Value (SINE) = **0,00000000**
PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/N) \times 100 = (2 / 17) \times 100 = 11,76 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (13 / 17) \times 100 = 76,47 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (0 / 17) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (2 / 17) \times 100 = 11,76 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (2 / 15) \times 100 = 13,33 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (13 / 15) \times 100 = 86,67 \%$
 $(c/ not A) \times 100 = (0 / 2) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$
 $(d/ not A) \times 100 = (2 / 2) \times 100 = 100,00 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (2 / 2) \times 100 = 100,00 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (0 / 2) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$
 $(b/ not B) \times 100 = (13 / 15) \times 100 = 86,67 \%$
 $(d/ not B) \times 100 = (2 / 15) \times 100 = 13,33 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (15 / 17) \times 100 = 88,24 \%$
 $(not A/N) \times 100 = (2 / 17) \times 100 = 11,76 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (2 / 17) \times 100 = 11,76 \%$
 $(not B/N) \times 100 = (15 / 17) \times 100 = 88,24 \%$
ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
RR (necessary condition) = Division by zero.
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,15384615
OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
Odds ratio (OR) = Division by zero.
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,13333333
STUDY DESIGN.
 $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,00000000$
 $p(\text{IOI}) = 0,76470588$

Kuo et al. are providing arguments supporting the hypothesis that CMV is a necessary condition for lung cancer.

4. Discussion

A CMV infection may be linked to various diseases, including lung cancer. Therefore, the development of a vaccine against CMV is imperative for substantially and enduringly decreasing the significant disease burden posed by CMV infections. Presently, there is no approved vaccine offering protection against CMV, even if numerous vaccine candidates^{25, 26} are undergoing evaluation in clinical trials. Possibly, the breakthrough²⁷ of mRNA-based²⁸ vaccinations²⁹ against the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) or COVID-19 disease with a fatality rate of about 2.19%³⁰ could accelerate efforts in this regard.

Based on the emerging evidence provided by this publication, it strongly suggests that cytomegalovirus (CMV) infection is a necessary condition for the development of lung cancer, indicating a crucial and causal role of CMV in lung carcinogenesis (P-Value = 0, see Table 1). However, the available data are somewhat inconsistent, and there are discrepancies in the reported sensitivity and specificity of the diagnostic methods used to detect CMV infection. Some studies indicate a strong relationship between CMV infection and lung cancer, while others report conflicting³¹ results. Furthermore, the sensitivity and specificity of the diagnostic tests employed in these studies are not always clearly stated, leading to uncertainty regarding the accuracy of the findings. Consequently, caution is warranted when interpreting the relationship between CMV infection and lung cancer as found in this

²⁵Smith LR, Wloch MK, Chaplin JA, Gerber M, Rolland AP. Clinical Development of a Cytomegalovirus DNA Vaccine: From Product Concept to Pivotal Phase 3 Trial. *Vaccines (Basel)*. 2013 Sep 25;1(4):398-414. doi: 10.3390/vaccines1040398. PMID: 26344340; PMCID: PMC4494211.

²⁶Pass RF, Zhang C, Evans A, Simpson T, Andrews W, Huang ML, Corey L, Hill J, Davis E, Flanigan C, Cloud G. Vaccine prevention of maternal cytomegalovirus infection. *N Engl J Med*. 2009 Mar 19;360(12):1191-9. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa0804749. PMID: 19297572; PMCID: PMC2753425.

²⁷Polack FP, Thomas SJ, Kitchin N, Absalon J, Gurtman A, Lockhart S, Perez JL, Pérez Marc G, Moreira ED, Zerbini C, Bailey R, Swanson KA, Roychoudhury S, Koury K, Li P, Kalina WV, Cooper D, Frenck RW Jr, Hammitt LL, Türeci Ö, Nell H, Schaefer A, Ünal S, Tresnan DB, Mather S, Dormitzer PR, Şahin U, Jansen KU, Gruber WC; C4591001 Clinical Trial Group. Safety and Efficacy of the BNT162b2 mRNA Covid-19 Vaccine. *N Engl J Med*. 2020 Dec 31;383(27):2603-2615. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2034577. Epub 2020 Dec 10. PMID: 33301246; PMCID: PMC7745181.

²⁸Baden LR, El Sahly HM, Essink B, Kotloff K, Frey S, Novak R, Diemert D, Spector SA, Rouphael N, Creech CB, McGettigan J, Khetan S, Segall N, Solis J, Brosz A, Fierro C, Schwartz H, Neuzil K, Corey L, Gilbert P, Janes H, Follmann D, Marovich M, Mascola J, Polakowski L, Ledgerwood J, Graham BS, Bennett H, Pajon R, Knightly C, Leav B, Deng W, Zhou H, Han S, Ivarsson M, Miller J, Zaks T, COVE Study Group. Efficacy and Safety of the mRNA-1273 SARS-CoV-2 Vaccine. *N Engl J Med*. 2021 Feb 4;384(5):403-416. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2035389. Epub 2020 Dec 30. PMID: 33378609; PMCID: PMC7787219.

²⁹Voysey M, Clemens SAC, Madhi SA, Weckx LY, Folegatti PM, Aley PK, Angus B, Baillie VL, Barnabas SL, Bhorat QE, Bibi S, Briner C, Cicconi P, Collins AM, Colin-Jones R, Cutland CL, Darton TC, Dheda K, Duncan CJA, Emary KRW, Ewer KJ, Fairlie L, Faust SN, Feng S, Ferreira DM, Finn A, Goodman AL, Green CM, Green CA, Heath PT, Hill C, Hill H, Hirsch I, Hodgson SHC, Izu A, Jackson S, Jenkin D, Joe CCD, Kerridge S, Koen A, Kwatra G, Lazarus R, Lawrie AM, Lelliott A, Libri V, Lillie PJ, Mallory R, Mendes AVA, Milan EP, Minassian AM, McGregor A, Morrison H, Mujadidi YF, Nana A, O'Reilly PJ, Padayachee SD, Pittella A, Plested E, Pollock KM, Ramasamy MN, Rhead S, Schwarzbold AV, Singh N, Smith A, Song R, Snape MD, Sprinz E, Sutherland RK, Tarrant R, Thomson EC, Török ME, Toshner M, Turner DPJ, Vekemans J, Villafana TL, Watson MEE, Williams CJ, Douglas AD, Hill AVS, Lambe T, Gilbert SC, Pollard AJ; Oxford COVID Vaccine Trial Group. Safety and efficacy of the ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine (AZD1222) against SARS-CoV-2: an interim analysis of four randomised controlled trials in Brazil, South Africa, and the UK. *Lancet*. 2021 Jan 9;397(10269):99-111. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)32661-1. Epub 2020 Dec 8. Erratum in: *Lancet*. 2021 Jan 9;397(10269):98. PMID: 33306989; PMCID: PMC7723445.

³⁰WHO-Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic

³¹Rashid S, Ardeljan A, Frankel LR, Cardeiro M, Kim E, Nagel BM, Takabe K, Rashid O. Human Cytomegalovirus (CMV) Infection Associated With Decreased Risk of Bronchogenic Carcinoma: Understanding How a Previous CMV Infection Leads to an Enhanced Immune Response Against Malignancy. *Cureus*. 2023 Apr 7;15(4):e37265. doi: 10.7759/cureus.37265. PMID: 37162767; PMCID: PMC10164441.

publication until further, and more systematic research can provide more definitive conclusions. However, this publication underscores the need for additional well-designed and highly systematic studies with robust methodologies to elucidate the role of CMV in lung carcinogenesis and to clarify any discrepancies in the existing data. Such research efforts will be crucial for informing clinical practice and guiding future therapeutic strategies targeting CMV-associated lung cancer.

5. Conclusion

Considering the considerable variation in the prevalence of CMV in lung cancer patients and tissues, there arises a question regarding the precise involvement of CMV in lung cancer carcinogenesis. This variability prompts further investigation to elucidate the true significance of CMV in the development of lung cancer. Consequently, additional research in this area holds promise for uncovering new insights into the relationship between CMV and lung cancer, potentially leading to advancements in our understanding and treatment of the disease. In the interim, we are authorized, albeit under only preliminary considerations, to assume the validity of the following hypothesis:

‘Without cytomegalovirus infection, no lung cancer.’

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections’ introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are frequently used:

CMV	Cytomegalovirus
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EBV	Epstein-Bar virus
IHC	Immunohistochemistry
ISH	In situ hybridization
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
BMI	body mass index
ESRD	end-stage renal disease
HD	hemodialysis
CABG	coronary artery bypass graft
CCI	Charlson comorbidity index
AMI	acute myocardial infarction
MACE	major adverse cardiovascular events
LDL-C	low-density lipoprotein cholesterol
GFR	glomerular filtration rate
STEMI	ST elevation myocardial infarction
NSTEMI	non-ST elevation myocardial infarction
MI	myocardial infarction
ARB	angiotensin receptor blocker
ACEI	angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors
CCBs	calcium channel blockers
IOR	index of relationship
p(IOU)	index of unfairness
p(IOI)	index of independence
k	Causal relationship
SINE	Necessary condition relationship
IMP	Sufficient condition relationship
EXCL	exclusion relationship
RR	Relative risk
RR (nc)	relative risk (necessary condition)
RR (sc)	relative risk (sufficient condition)
OR	Odds ratio
P Value	Probability of significance

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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